

The Creation of Contemporary Apparel Inspired by the Structural Pattern Sofa Vimanmek Mansion

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Abstract—In most of apparel creation, the designer usually uses standard pattern as a fundamental of pattern making. In the design of each kind of apparel, standard pattern is starting point of production. The importance of standard pattern is that it is able to have the apparel fits to general people. Therefore, standard pattern is standardized to be the same. Regardless which type of apparel, its standard pattern will have similar production. Anyhow, the author sees that the apparel design, regardless for which type of apparel, has to stick on the standard pattern as a fundamental of apparel design and this seems to be a limitation of apparel design without any designing alternative being developed. In the research on the creation of contemporary apparel inspired by the sofa's pattern structure in Vimanmek Mansion. The author has applied the pattern of the sofa and armchair to be the principle in the apparel design, instead of standard pattern, to create new form of structures and shapes making the contemporary apparel becomes more interesting and different than previous, can be used in daily life, as well as being a new alternative for apparel design. Those who are interesting in such idea can apply and develop it to be more variety further.

Keywords—Contemporary Apparel, Sofa's Pattern, Armchair's Pattern, Vimanmek Mansion.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN designing clothes, there should be new options for various ways of designing without considering the same old standard pattern used at present. [1] New options for designing clothes should be increased by using pattern structure made from other materials which have the pattern resembling the clothes. This is in order to develop contemporary clothing pattern which is novel and can actually be worn in everyday life.

From the above-mentioned ideas, the researcher has noticed the methods of applying patterns from other material structures, for ex: sofas, armchairs, to be suitably used with clothes and can actually be worn. This is the same as the world's leading couturier such as Hussein Chalayan who develops and changes the sofa patterns into ultramodern clothes (having novel pattern). Thus designing clothes do not need to always occur from standard pattern.

The furniture like sofas has production characteristics and process extremely similar to clothing production: raw materials, some part of figure, and some stages of production techniques (for ex: detailed techniques of sewing hem and seams, and enveloping sofas which are popular in various

places and buildings including museums and throne halls) [2]. Since sofas have continuously been in development of modern design for a long time: both contours and materials used for decoration as well as usage benefits. All of these are methods which can be used to apply with clothing production process appropriately.

Fig. 1 Vimanmek Mansion

Fig. 2 Sofa and armchair in Vimanmek Mansion

The researcher thus chose sofas and armchairs in Vimanmek Mansion to be used as inspiration in designing contemporary clothes to be the research title since the mansion has beautiful and elaborate architectural characteristics and receives western construction influence [3]. Most furniture used in the mansion was imported from European countries, so sofas and armchairs would possess Victorian art patterns [4]. Thus it is very interesting to use the study results of sofa and armchair patterns in Vimanmek Mansion as inspiration in designing contemporary women's clothes which are developed from modification of sofa and armchair pattern structure to be able to actually and appropriately be worn in everyday life.

There has never been the research emphasizing the women's clothing design with the inspiration of sofa pattern structure in Vimanmek Mansion. Most researches or works

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are only done in the form of books detailing history of various throne halls or of special books. This research work is very important since it is the developmental conservation of Thailand's Ratanakosin art and culture which has to be valued highly for the posterity. The researcher has made the research project titled "the creation of contemporary women's clothes inspired by the pattern structure of sofas in Vimanmek Mansion: studying particular patterns and contours of pattern structure in backrest valances and valances of sofas and armchairs in Vimanmek Mansion"

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

- 1) To study and find methods of clothing design using new pattern making derived from the form of pattern making of sofas and armchairs, to modify those patterns into clothes, and to apply the sofa material to make appropriate clothes.
- 2) To study the history of form and pattern structure of sofas and armchairs in Vimanmek Mansion in order to be used as inspiration in designing contemporary women's clothes.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- 1) Collecting data from studying documents at the National Library, Archive Center of various educational institutions' libraries, and other concerned agencies.
- 2) Collecting data from field study at Vimanmek Mansion.
- 3) Collecting data from sub-group conversations with the expert (receiving the expert's opinions).
- 4) Analyzing the data derived from study and using it as the inspiration in designing contemporary women's clothes.
- 5) Presenting the results of data analysis and research in the form of descriptive research together with 10 sets of illustrations (pictures) and actually producing 10 suits of contemporary women's clothes.

IV. RESULT OF THE RESEARCH

According to the research result arranging creative media in the form of producing 10 suits contemporary women's clothes inspired by the pattern structure of sofas in Vimanmek Mansion, and studying the holistic knowledge acquired from the research in order to disseminate it to the general public through print media and exhibition.

A. The Summary of 10 Styles

Fig. 3 Inspiration Board

Fig. 4 Target group Board

Fig. 5 Style 1

Fig. 6 Style 2

Fig. 7 Style 3

Fig. 11 Style 7

Fig. 8 Style 4

Fig. 12 Style 8

Fig. 9 Style 5

Fig. 13 Style 9

Fig. 10 Style 6

Fig. 14 Style 10

B. Bringing the Research Result to be Useful

Fig. 15 Exhibition presentation of research results in Thailand Graduate Fashion Week 2011: 16-19 September 2011

Fig. 16 Fashion show presentation of research results in KNACK: The 5th Aesthete: 26 September 2011

Fig. 17 Presentation of research results in The First Higher Education Research Promotion Congress (HERP CONGRESS I): 21-23 January 2013

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